

Effect of Gamma Radiation on Pure Paraffin Wax and on Wax-Acetone System

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The structure of Iraqi paraffin wax is found to be straight chain with no branching or unsaturation, with an average formula of $C_{54}H_{70}$ and an average molecular weight of 471. The effect of gamma radiation on pure wax is to give degradation products containing some unsaturation. Cross-linking of these fragments, which occurs at 60 Mrads, give products of molecular weight less than twice the original. The effect on wax-acetone system (an emulsion) is that no degradation or cross-linking is observed, using up to 115.2 Mrads, thus there is complete protection by acetone. This emulsion case has not been reported before, and the Domain Effect is used for its explanation.

The effect of gamma radiation on pure paraffin wax depends on the structure of the wax used. Generally the effects are similar to those obtained when paraffins of low or high molecular weights are subjected to gamma radiation^{1,2}, a great variety of products of higher and lower molecular weights than the original substances, comprising both saturated and unsaturated compounds are obtained.

Various problems of practical and theoretical importance are involved in the radiolysis of solutions, as the energy transfer processes which occur in the irradiation of multicomponent systems, and also the behaviour of solute molecules under attack by free radicals.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The structure of paraffin wax :

The wax used in this study was obtained from Dora Petroleum Refineries, Baghdad, Iraq, whose petroleum comes from Kirkuk Oil Fields. Purified Dora wax has the elemental analysis of 85.70% C and 14.26% H, its average molecular weight is 471, and its m.p. is 67°.

The nuclear magnetic resonance spectra of this wax show a peak at 1.25δ which is due to the CH_2 group, and a peak at 0.88δ which is that of the CH_3 group. From their integration lines, the ratio of the CH_2/CH_3 is found to be 10.8, corresponding to a saturated straight chain molecule, with an average formula of $C_{34}H_{70}$. This structure is similar to that of polyethylene, which has a single resonance signal from equivalent CH_2 group at $1.27\delta^3$.

The infra-red spectra of the Dora wax show the CH_3 asymmetric deformation band at 1375 cm^{-1} , and the combined asymmetric deformation of the CH_3 and the scissoring vibration of the CH_2 group at 1463 cm^{-1} . The ratio of the intensities of the CH_2/CH_3 bands is 8.2, a large value, which is characteristic of long-straight chains⁴.

The effect of gamma radiation on pure wax :

The effect of gamma radiation from Co⁶⁰ on pure wax in the solid state, under vacuum, at $\sim 40^\circ$, is given in table 1. The total doses used varied from 0.60 to 115.2 Mrads, at a dose-rate of 166 rad/sec. There is a linear drop in the m.p. followed by a rise as the dose is increased. The small decrease in the m.p. is due either to the formation of branched chain structure or to the production of lower paraffins, by main-chain fracture, the paraffins

TABLE 1

Sample No.	Total dose, rads.	M.pt. °C	Turbidity point °C	%C	%H	Mol. Wt.	Formula
1	0.60 $\times 10^6$	67	26.5	85.44	14.67	529	C ₃₉ H ₇₈
2	2.70 =	69	27.0	85.25	14.45	516	C ₃₇ H ₇₆
3	14.40 =	67	23.5	85.21	14.51	548	C ₃₉ H ₈₀
4	57.60 =	63	19.5	85.17	14.46	559	C ₄₀ H ₈₁
5a	103.20 =	70	27.5	85.19	14.62	680	C ₄₈ H ₉₆
5	115.20 =	76	28.0				

containing double bonds. Although the M.pt.s. decrease initially but the molecular weights increase, as shown in table 1, this is in line with the observation made by Charlesby using much higher doses, up to ~ 1350 Mrads, and noting the increase in m.p. at ~ 1000 Mrads⁵. While in this work, the increase in the m.p. is observed at 58 Mrads (from a plot of m.p. vs. dose, not shown) with a molecular weight of 559, compared with 471 for the unirradiated wax. The molecular weights are lying between the monomer and dimer, this is due to small number of cross-links taking place.

The turbidity point in this work is defined as the temperature at which the clear solution of wax in benzene becomes turbid. Changes in turbidity points are parallel to those in the m.p., suggesting similar explanations.

All the irradiated samples are pale yellow which is due to the formation of double bonds, in agreement with the fact that polyethylene (and most polymers) becomes yellow after ~ 10 Mrads⁶.

The NMR spectra of 20% solution of the irradiated waxes in CCl₄, show no peak at 4.7δ , indicating that the extent of unsaturation involved is very small, less than 1% since the spectrum of a 1% cyclohexene—CCl₄ solution has a small unsaturation peak at 4.3δ . The CH₂/CH₃ ratio, from integration lines, is the same for the irradiated and the unirradiated wax samples, indicating that no branching is taking place on irradiation.

The infrared spectra of samples nos. 4 and 5, clearly show the C = C stretching bands at 1659 and 1689 cm⁻¹ and the C = C bending band at 1709 cm⁻¹; these bands are due to the non-conjugated and the conjugated double bonds respectively.

The Effect of Gamma Radiation on the Wax-acetone System :

The effect of gamma radiation on the mixture (emulsion) of wax and acetone is summarised in table 2. The purpose of this part is to find the effect of added reactive intermediates on irradiated wax. Acetone was chosen because it gives many reactive intermediates in the liquid state on irradiation, as it was summarised in ref. (7) : $\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3^+$, e^- , CH_3CO^+ , $\text{CH}_3\text{C}\dot{\text{O}}$, $\text{CH}_3\cdot$, $\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{COCH}_3$, $\text{H}\cdot$, etc. Results of table 2, show, unexpectedly, that these species have no effect on wax, since there is no change in the molecular weights of samples nos. 6 and 7 from the original wax, and also the infra-red spectra of these samples show no

TABLE 2

One Gram of Wax plus One ml. of Acetone in Each Sample (1 : 6 molar ratio)

Sample No.	Total dose, rads.	M.pt. °C	Turbidity point °C	%C	%H	Mol. Wt.	Formula
6	14.4×10^6	71	25.0	85.34	14.42	464	$\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{68}$
7	57.6 =	72	27.0	85.23	14.32	470	$\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{70}$
8	115.2 =	76	28.5	85.35	14.48	496	$\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{72}$

unsaturation bands. The explanation of this result may be sought out in the energy transfer from wax to acetone, *i.e.*, that acetone is showing a very good protective effect. However the deactivation of excited molecules by acetone has been known in solutions only⁸, and not in emulsions as is the case of this study. The protective effect of acetone on the degradation of polymethyl methacrylate and polyvinyl chloride was explained as due to the fact that the optical absorption of acetone extends to longer wave-lengths than that of the solute, leading to the deactivation of the excited solute molecules. This optical approximation rule is critically discussed by Kroh *et al.*². Similarly, in the wax-acetone system, the excited wax molecules on the surface of the wax particle in the emulsion may be deactivated by acetone molecules. However, it is difficult to explain why the wax bulk inside these particles does not undergo any change on irradiation, while pure wax show large effects. To explain this, an argument similar to that of the collective excitation introduced by Fano⁹ may be used. The initial excitation tends to spread over larger regions and finally deactivated by acetone :

The several activated wax molecules are forming what may be called a domain through which excitation spreads rapidly¹⁰; this domain is treated as a unit collisionally equivalent to an individual excited molecule.

The molecular weight of wax increased only slightly after irradiating to 115.2 Mrads. The infra-red spectra show a band at $\sim 1707 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating unsaturation. In this case wax emulsion in acetone is behaving as pure wax, but to a reduced extent. This may be due to the gradual removal of acetone molecules by decomposition after this long irradiation, resulting in loss of protection. In fact the wax in this sample looked lumpy.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Pure paraffin wax was obtained by repeated precipitations from boiling *n*-hexane; cooled to room temperature, frozen and filtered. Drying was done in a drying pistol. All samples are irradiated under vacuum (using an oil pump which gives 10^{-2} mm pressure) in quartz tubes, in the Gamma Cell 220, fitted with Co^{60} , the strength of which is 0.6 Mrads per hour, calculated by the ferrous chemical dosimetric method..

The turbidity point is determined by dissolving 0.1 g of wax in 16.0 ml of benzene; the mixture contained in a conical flask and provided with a thermometer, is heated by a steam bath until it becomes clear. Then cooled gradually until it becomes turbid, and the temperature of turbidity is observed.

The A60-Varian spectrometer is used for the NMR work, at a probe temperature of 37° . The H 800 Hilger and Watts recording spectrophotometer is used for the infra-red work, calibrated with polystyrene film. Infra-red spectra are mostly taken for thin film, some samples contained a few drops of CCl_4 .

The wax-acetone emulsion is prepared by mixing with a glass rod at 40° , 1.0 g of wax and 1 ml of acetone. The evacuation and sealing of the tubes are carried out using liquid nitrogen. The acetone is removed, after irradiation, by evacuation under vacuum at 70° to 80° for 30 min.

All solvents used are of Analar or spectrosol grade. The chemical analysis and molecular weights determinations (by the Rast method) were all done by Alfrad Bernhard's Laboratories, Ruhr, W. Germany.

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R E F E R E N C E S

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